

GANDBOL SANOAT VA TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya. Gandbol sohasi yillar davomida qandaydir strategik va tizimli qadamlar tashlash natijasida shakllandi. Bu borada professionallikni qabul qilish, katta zallar qurish masalan, hokimiyatning o'yinga bo'lgan qiziqishi, gandbolni millat davlatlarining ramzlaridan biriga aylantirish, gandbol bilan bog'liq yangi sohalarni rivojlantirish (tikish, sport anjomlarini ommalashtirish, ommaviy axborot vositalariga qiziqishning ortishi va boshqalar) o'yin iqtisodiy qiymati oshishi sabablari orasida ko'rib chiqilishi mumkin. Gandbol sanoatlashtirish jarayoni jadal sifatida, gandbol iqtisodiyoti o'sdi; shafqatsiz raqobat muhiti mavjudligi, shuningdek, gandbol sohasida qo'llaniladigan; endi u o'ynash va zavq uchun jun hisoblanadi biroq, g'alaba qozonish va erishish birinchi o'ringa chiqdi. Gandbol natijaga yo'naltirilgan o'yinga aylanganda, xatolarni minimallashtirish uchun yangi dasturlar joriy etildi.

Ushbu maqolada ikkilamchi manbalardan olingan adabiyotlar sharhi o'tkazildi. 21 asr boshidan beri ulkan sanoatga aylangan gandbol o'zining iqtisodiy qiymatini saqlab qolish uchun texnologiyadan foydalanishi kerak "" taklif tushuntirildi.

Kalit So'zlar: Gandbol, Texnologiya, Sanoat gandboli, Sport.

USE OF HANDBALL INDUSTRY AND TECHNOLOGY

Abstract. The field of handball has been formed as a result of taking some strategic and systematic steps over the years. In this regard, adopting professionalism, building large halls, for example, the authorities' interest in the game, making handball one of the symbols of the nation-state, developing new areas related to handball (betting, popularizing sports equipment, increasing interest in the media, etc.) can be considered among the reasons for the increase in the economic value of the game. As the handball industrialization process accelerated, the handball economy grew; the existence of an atmosphere of brutal competition, which is also used in the field of handball; now it is wool for playing and pleasure, but winning and achieving came to the fore. As handball became a result-oriented game, new programs were introduced to minimize mistakes.

In this article, a review of literature from secondary sources was conducted. "Handball, which has become a huge industry since the beginning of the 21st century, must use technology to maintain its economic value," the proposal explained.

Keywords: Handball, Technology, Industrial handball, Sport.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ГАНДБОЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация. Сфера гандбола сформировалась в результате принятия на протяжении многих лет ряда стратегических и систематических шагов. В связи с этим, принятие профессионализма, строительство больших залов, например, интерес властей к игре, превращение гандбола в один из символов национального государства, развитие новых направлений, связанных с гандболом (беттинг, популяризация спортивного инвентаря, повышение интереса к СМИ и т. д.) можно считать одной из причин увеличения

экономической ценности игры. По мере ускорения процесса индустриализации гандбола экономика гандбола росла; существование атмосферы жестокой конкуренции, которая используется и в сфере гандбола; сейчас это шерсть для игры и удовольствия, но на первый план вышли победы и достижения. Поскольку гандбол стал игрой, ориентированной на результат, были введены новые программы, позволяющие минимизировать ошибки.

В данной статье был проведен обзор литературы из вторичных источников. «Гандбол, который с начала XXI века превратился в огромную индустрию, должен использовать технологии, чтобы сохранить свою экономическую ценность», — поясняется в предложении.

Ключевые слова: Гандбол, Технологии, Промышленный гандбол, Спорт.

Kirish. Gandbol iqtisodiyoti gandbol ortib bormoqda deb, sanoatlashtirish jarayonini tezlashtiradi; gandbol maydon raqobat muhiti achinish siz borligi uchun amal qiladi; endi o'ynaydi, g'alaba olish va oldinga kelib erishish uchun emas, balki industrlashtirish bilan investitsiya maydoniga aylangan gandbol endi faqat natija va natijalar orqali qo'lga kiritiladigan ijara o'yiniga aylanib bormoqda. Xatolarni minimallashtirish uchun yangi dasturlar, chunki gandbol natijaga yo'naltirilgan o'yinga aylanadi aktivlashtirilmogda.

Iqtisodiy blokada oshirish globallashuv o'zgartirish bilan o'yin qoidalarini qo'llash tez-tez xatolar sanoati gandbol hakam gandbol yanada shaffof va ishonchli qilish uchun juda yuqori istak bo'lishi mikrofon qadriyatlar yo'qolgan, hakam qiyin vazifalar texnologik qo'llab-quvvatlash zarurligini ochib beradi. Bizning maqolamizda gandbol va gandbol sohasida texnologiyalar yaratadigan o'zgarishlarni gandbolda qo'llaniladigan texnologiyalar misollari, adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish va amalda misollar bilan tushuntirishga harakat qilamiz.

Gandbolni industrlashtirish jarayoni

So'nggi o'ttiz yil ichida gandbolni sanoatlashtirish sodir bo'ldi. Gandbolni 'biznes' holatiga aylantirish jarayonini tezlashtirgan rivojlanish 2005-2006 yilgi mavsumda boshlangan amaliyoti edi. Uning tashkiliy tuzilishi, tabiati va moliyaviy hajmi ham u o'zgartirildi va tadbirning shou tomonini ish bilan birlashtirib, sportning sanoat o'lchovi birinchi o'ringa ko'tarildi. Ushbu turnir va reytingga bo'lgan qiziqish yanada yuqori bo'lishini ta'minlash uchun u Evropaning asosiy ligalarida mashhurgarchi jamoalar chempion bo'la olmagan bo'lsalar-da, ular ushbu musobaqaga kiritilgan.

Gandbol, ommaviy axborot vositalari va texnologiyalar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga nazariy qarash

Ommaviy axborot vositalari va transport vositalari va modernizmning rivojlanishi o'xshashliklarni ko'rsatdi. Bo'sh vaqtlarini gazeta o'qish, radio tinglash, televizor tomosha qilish orqali baholay boshlagan omma bu vositalarga ko'proq "qaram" bo'la boshladi.

Ommaboplik professionalizatsiyani keltirib chiqardi, bu ommaviy axborot vositalarida tabloid elementi sifatida ommalashgan ushbu sport turidan foydalanishni ko'payishiga olib keldi.

Gazetadan keyin efirga uzatishni boshlagan radio va ayniqsa televizor bizning uylarimiz o'rtasiga o'rnatilganligi va ularning samaradorligini asta-sekin oshirib borishi televizorni tomosha qilishni zamonaviy jamiyatlarning eng muhim bo'sh vaqt faoliyatiga aylantirdi. 1950-yillardan boshlab televidenie ommaviy axborot vositalariga aylandi. Ommaviy axborot vositalari, ayniqsa

televidenie, bo'sh vaqtni tashkil qilish va ommani nazorat ostida ushlab turish uchun hatto shaharlardan tashqariga chiqadi u tadbirga kirish huquqiga ega edi va televizor bilan birgalikda uylar zamonaviy dunyodagi eng muhim bo'sh joylardan biriga aylandi.

Televizor bilan bog'langanidan so'ng, gandbolning hayotimizga ta'siri darajasi oshdi. Gandbolda tovarlashtirish jarayoni tezlashgandan so'ng shakllangan 'yangi gandbol' naqshlari bilan gandbol bizning iste'mol naqshlarimizni shakllantiradigan maydonga aylandi. Televizor bilan bog'langanidan so'ng, gandbolning hayotimizga ta'siri darajasi oshdi. Gandbolda tovarlashtirish jarayoni tezlashgandan so'ng shakllangan 'yangi gandbol' naqshlari bilan gandbol bizning iste'mol naqshlarimizni shakllantiradigan maydonga aylandi. Ushbu jarayonda tomoshabinlar profili, daromadlar varaqalari va gandbolga yuklangan ma'no/qiymat naqshlari o'zgardi.

Gandbol asta-sekin televizor, homiylik va reklama orqali shakllangan uchburchakda o'ynaladigan o'yinga aylandi. Gandbolni ushbu uch xil segmentga qarab aniqlash, xususan, televizorga bog'liqligini oshirdi. Buning natijasida ko'proq daromad keltiradigan tashkilotlarni tashkil qilish uchun sportchilar ko'proq kuch sarflashadi, ko'proq o'yin o'ynashadi.

Gandbolda texnologiyalardan foydalanish

Yangi OAV va texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi dunyoda mashhur sport turi bo'lgan gandbol texnologiyadan eng ko'p foydalanadigan sport turidan biri bo'lishini ta'minladi. Gandbol maydonidan tashqari, gandbolchilar, o'quv modellari va tahlillari ham texnologiya ta'sirida bo'lgan.

Chunki professionalizatsiya jarayoni bilan birga o'yinchilar, jamoalar, o'yin o'tkaziladigan joylar, jamoalar va menejerlarning boshqaruv uslublari ham o'zgardi. Pul birinchi o'ringa chiqadigan ushbu yangi jarayonda tovarlashtirish hayotning barcha sohalarida, sportda tajribali unga tegishli barcha qadriyatlar va hukmlarning qayta qurilishiga olib keldi. Klublar endi aktsiyadorlik jamiyatlari singari boshqariladigan ro'yxatga olingan kompaniyalarga aylanishdi.

Texnologiya sport zallarda tomlariga joylashtirilgan kameralar yordamida to'pning harakatlarini kuzatishga qaratilgan ken to'pning GoalRef sensorlari bilan chiziqni kesib o'tganligini aniqlashga harakat qilmoqda.

Adidas'ning chempionlik uchun ishlab chiqargan to'pi ham turli texnologiyalar bilan jihozlangan. Frantsuz tilida "chiroyli o'yin" degan ma'noni anglatuvchi "Beau Jeu" nomli to'p o'zining yangi ishlab chiqilgan yuqori to'qimasi bilan ko'proq ushlanishni ta'minlaydi. Undagi ranglar, shuningdek, darvozabonlar uchun katta ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan va parvoz paytida to'pning harakatlarini yaxshiroq kuzatishga imkon beradigan ko'zni qamashtiradigan soyalardan tanlanadi.

Boshqa tomondan, texnologiya Stade De France o'tiga ham hissa qo'shdi. Desso Master System deb nomlangan usul bilan tabiiy o'tlarning ildizlari butun maydon bo'ylab 2 million plastik tolalar bilan qo'llab-quvvatlanib, o'tlarning sifati butun maydon bo'ylab bir xil darajada saqlanib turishini va ularning yanada mustahkam bo'lishini ta'minlaydi.

Ayniqsa, yangi texnologiyalarning jadal joriy etilishi gandbolning tijoratlashtirish va tovarlashtirish o'qida yana shakllana boshlashi bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Dekindustrializatsiya jarayonida ko'ngilochar sanoat va gandbol o'rtasida hamkorlik o'rnatildi. Gandbol klublari media-ko'ngil ochar uni dunyo sotib ola boshladi.

Hakamlar uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish

Garchi gandbolga texnologiyani joriy etishga qarshilik ko'rsatgan bo'lsa-da, gandbol o'yinlarini muvaffaqiyatli boshqarish, xatoliklarni kamaytirish va standart yo'nalishni tushunishni yaxshilash uchun texnologiya gandbolga kirishi kerakligini tushuldi. Hakamlarni gandbolda texnologiyaga kiritish signal bayroqlaridan foydalanish bilan boshlandi. O'yinlarda signalli bayroqdan foydalanish hakamlarni juda yengillashtirdi, o'yin va hakamlar rahbariyatiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi hissa qo'shdi. Hakamlarga birinchi marta taqdim etilgan ushbu kichik texnologik yordam ijobiy natijalar berdi.

Maqsad chizig'i texnologiyasi hakamning qarorini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadi bor-yo'qligini tekshirish uchun ishlatiladi. Yilda darvoza chizig'i texnologiya, elektro-nic sxemalari to'pga joylashtirilgan, magnit datchiklar esa darvoza chizig'idagi darvoza ustunlariga birlashtirilgan va unga parallel. Agar sensorlar butun to'p chiziqni kesib o'tganligini aniqlasa, hakamning soati 1 soniya ichida ogohlantiriladi.

Ishlashni yaxshilash uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish

Texnologiya bilan bir qatorda o'quv modellari ham o'zgarib bormoqda. Gandbol klublari texnologiyadan foydalanadilar, ayniqsa infratuzilma ob'ektlarida, bu borada eng aniq va chor pici tizimi so'nggi ikki yil ichida gandbol klublari tomonidan tashkil etilgan. "Gandboltbonaut" deb nomlangan tizimni joriy qilgan klub, ayniqsa, tizim bilan yosh gandbolchilarning texnik imkoniyatlarini oshirishni maqsad qilgan. Tizim kub shaklida u maydon modelidan iborat.

Ikkala misol ham "yulduz" o'yinchilarni yaratish, u bilan ommaviy harakatchanlikni oshirish va natijada tizim tomonidan dinamikdan foydalanish va gandbol klublari tomonidan afzal ko'rish uchun yaratilgan gandbol klublari ham ushbu shuhratdan olishlari mumkin bo'lgan maksimal qiymatni olishadi. Chunki, yuqorida aytib o'tganimizdek, bugungi kunda gandbol klublari kompaniya mantig'i bilan ishlaydi.

Natijada

Sanoatlashtirish bilan investitsiya maydoni va vositasiga aylangan gandbol endi faqat natija va natijadan olinadigan ijara uchun o'ynaydi. Klublar hakamlarning noto'g'ri qarorlari bilan ularning katta xarajatlari behuda ketishini istamaydilar; katta annuitetlar yo'naltirilgan sektorda inson omili mavjud ekan, xatolarni hech qachon tiklash mumkin emasligi qabul qilinmaydi.

Biroq, gandbol-bu ikki tomonlama jangga ma'lum darajada ruxsat berilgan o'yin. Shuning uchun tezkor aloqalar va murakkab pozitsiyalar to'g'ri bo'lishini ta'minlash muhimdir uni filtrlash har doim ham mumkin emas.

Hozirgi kunda xatoliklarni kamaytirish va gandbol o'yinlarini muvaffaqiyatli boshqarish uchun standart boshqaruv tushunchasini takomillashtirish texno-mantiqiy yordamisiz mumkin emas deb hisoblanadi. Muayyan xatolar yuz berganda texnologik yordam hakamlarga ham, jamoalarga ham yordam beradi.

Texnologiya orqali gandbol sanoatining aktyorlari, masalan, gandbolni sevuvchilar yoki mijozlarni xursand qilish, ularni stadionlarga jalb qilish, ko'proq reklama tomosha qilish, ko'proq mahsulot sotib olishga imkon berish nashriyot tashkilotga xizmat qiladigan ko'plab ob'ektlarni taqdim etishda davom etadi.

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